

21st Century Pedagogy: Transformational Approach

Novelita T. Bornea¹, Ma. Georgina B. Español², Ma. May A. Buala³, Pedrito S. Ocba Jr⁴

^{1,2,3}Faculty, Department of Education, Cebu, Philippines

⁴Faculty, Cebu Technological University, Cebu, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Pedagogies are constantly evolving and great emphasis has been laid on the teachers to use effective teaching strategies and method to improve students' achievement. That is why pedagogy is one of the important factors that need to revisit in order to maximize the attainment of educational objectives. Based on the data gathered, technology in the classroom, differentiated instruction and student centered approach should be adapted and modeled across the country to elevate and nourish the capability of the students to go beyond limitation. Further, the way students learn and comprehend have change dramatically; educators must also evolve from traditional way to 21st century way of teaching.

KEYWORDS: Pedagogy, 21st Century, Transformational, Learning

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INTRODUCTION

Preparing students in the 21st century is complicated. Research indicates that effective teachers are the most essential factor contributing to students' success. Although curricula, reduced type size, district funding, household and community involvement all make a contribution to school improvement and student achievement, the most influential issue is the teacher. Choosing tremendous teachers is critically important for schools trying to improve their performance (Parihar, 2011). Few topics in education have captured as abundant attention from policymakers and practitioners as the association between teaching quality and student success. The analysis has clearly shown that quality teaching matters to student learning. Teacher quality has been systematically known as the foremost vital school-based think about student success (McCaffrey et al. 2002).

Teacher effectiveness plays an important role in teaching learning process. An effective teacher does not create image of the students rather help the students to create the image of their own by understanding the problems of the students and helping them by making any subject interesting, by controlling the class and by being fair with the students while dealing with them.

Having a well thought-out pedagogy will improve the standard of your teaching and also the means students learn, serving to them gain a deeper grasp of elementary material. Being aware of the means you teach will assist you higher perceive however facilitate students deliver the goods deeper learning. And it can, in turn, impact student perception, leading to cooperative learning environments (Persaud, 2019).

According to the Florida State University (2017) teaching effectively involves not only the use of tools, techniques, and strategies to optimize student learning but an understanding of context, in particular how your students learn, how they process information, what motivates them to learn more, and what impedes the learning process.

The way toward assessing the viability of teachers has changed after some time alongside the meaning of what viable instructing is, expected to some extent to expanding state and government consideration regarding school-level and homeroom level responsibility for students learning. Compelling teaching has been characterized in differently (Campbell, Kyriakides, Muijs, and Robinson, 2003; Cheng and Tsui, 1999; Cruickshank and Haeefe, 1990; Great, 1996; Muijs, 2006), and strategies for estimating teachers have changed as definitions and convictions about what is imperative to quantify have developed. In spite of the fact that there is a general accord that great training matters and that it might be the absolute most significant school-based factor in improving students accomplishment (Sweetheart Hammond, 2000; Wright, Horn, and Sanders, 1997), estimating educator viability has stayed subtle to a limited extent as a result of continuous discussion about what an effective instruction is and does.

According to (Finzi, 2018) noted that teaching strategy would be the methods of instruction used by the teacher to help students to learn and to apply their knowledge to achieve their academic goals. Strategies are defined as the specific methods of approaching a problem or task, the modes of

operation for achieving a particular need and the planned designs for controlling and manipulating certain information (Brown,2007). The teacher must take into account the age of the students, their level, the setting of the class, the length of the class and the curriculum. The teacher might use different teaching aids to reach all students with different learning styles and abilities. Hye (2019) stated that training strategy is a strategy that used to help students in learning the ideal course substance and have the option to create reachable objectives later on. Rosenshine and frust (1973) reported that students learn best when the following characteristics are present: variability in techin methods and materials, interest, clarity, task oriented behavior, teacher use of structuring comments, student opportunity to learn the material, multiple level of questions and enthusiasm.

Jalbani (2014) viewed that stakeholders throughout the world take a stab at quality instruction of students. Most importantly, there is a need to characterize quality training with the goal that one can separate it from less-favored instruction. Essentially, there are numerous educators and analysts who have discussed that there are some school factors which impact the students' accomplishment. As per Coleman (2003), insignificant job is played by the schools the extent that the srudents' accomplishment is concerned in light of the fact that it is autonomous of their experience just as cultural variables. Then again, a couple of scientists recommend that components like class size and space (Glass 2001), the teachers' capability (Ferguson, 2004), the school's size and space (Haller, 1993), and a couple of more factors assume a crucial job in what the students learn in general.

Research brings up that quality instructing are will in general fundamentally be student focused. It expects to support most and for all students achievement. Along these lines, center ought not exclusively be educational abilities, yet additionally learning condition that must address the students' close to personal needs. students ought to likewise know with respect to why they are working so they can identify with different students and get help whenever required. Thus, extraordinary accentuation has been laid on "quality instructing" by numerous teachers. Similarly, there is a need of explaining the expression "quality instructing". Globalization has affected each and everybody's life. Quality, fruitful and viable adapting really relies upon a few elements for example accessibility and choice of instructional assets, staffing quality, nature and its level, proficient improvement suggestion as a framework, and furthermore the help of guardians and organization. As of late, look into likewise features one of the key highlights of "value educating" for example understudy focused study halls, which plans to profit all understudies learning (Jalbani, 2014). In this way, learning condition alongside educators' academic aptitudes is significant for quality instruction (Johnson, 2007). So also, the students have likewise gotten both, geologically and socially broadened. There is an extraordinary need of new showing strategies and instructional methods to address worldwide difficulties. Subsequently, we can say that there is additionally a need of progress in the student and educators' methods for communication. Every one of the schools are endeavoring to coordinate educational plan with innovation so the understudies are given quality training and learning happens their direction and they are centering to give quality instruction to the understudies by every one of the methods so they are ahead in the training business.

The greater part of the instructors feel that they can improve their teaching practices through creating sound information on content that should be educated and conveyed (Slope and Crevola, 2003). This is a significant downside in numerous schools. The instructors lose center around their encouraging systems and they accept that the students face troubles in light of the fact that the substance (what should be educated and conveyed) is confused or not of their enthusiasm, rather than understanding the way that the showing technique (how to educate and convey) ought to be increasingly viable and according to their necessity and needs so as to create their advantage and better learning open door for the understudies. Besides, both, how and what are connected together yet at the same time far various and special in nature.

Every one of the educationists are well acquainted with the way that every one of the students have an alternate learning style, though the issue lies in obliging every one of them with a viable instructing system. Understudies learn in various manners according to their capacities. Some learn by observing, hearing, reflecting, displaying, thinking, and drawing and so on (Felder, 1998). With a consent to Felder, comparably there are diverse showing styles also. Some give addresses, some talk about the theme, some make their understudies work in gatherings, some utilization innovation, some utilization course books and some more. Yet, the principle reason behind these endeavors is to assist understudies with getting a handle on content information and adjust them to this present reality situation.

Teaching strategies shift starting with one age bunch then onto the next. None of the strategy is the best. It relies upon the learning style of students. Essential students look into the exercises acted in the class. In-class practices work the best for this age gathering. Visual and sound-related guides improve learning and execution. Though, for auxiliary and tertiary levels, addresses, ventures, field work, bunch activities and friend educating are the most appropriate techniques to support them. Howard Gardner's various insights are additionally being considered and coordinated in the exercise plans for improved learning of every single student (Jalbani, 2014).

Moreover, vast related study has been laid on great emphasis has been laid on the educators to utilize compelling teaching strategy to improved student learning. This research article would like to disseminate informational best practices in relation to teaching strategies that elevate the students' achievement in the advent of 21st century teaching and learning.

DISCUSSIONS IMPLEMENT TECHNOLOGY

The capacity to not just find out about the new instructive devices that will assist students learn better and faster, but to also have the ability to know how to use and implement the gadget within the classroom is an essential skill of a 21st century educator. An effective educator will have the know-how and the wherewithal of how to efficiently (Cox, 2019). According to Mace (2018) traditionally, the teacher is the center of instruction. In a 21st century classroom, instructional technology provides the opportunity for each student to make choices over their own learning. Making a choice provides student ownership over what is learned. In

each of the three categories of instructional technology activities (practice, creativity, and discovery), there are opportunities for students to make choices.

Use Technology to Empower Students by using blended learning

Technology supports imaginative expression. Engaged students are those who actively express opinions, and don't just passively 'receive wisdom'. (Gupta, 2016). Technology can give them a platform to explain their ideas, not just regurgitate facts. Apart from this you can help students reach out and learn more. Social media helps you connect to people around the world and you can get in touch with experts. Pulse learning (2017) stated that whether you are teaching students or training employees, blended learning works because it can make your teaching more effective.

Online Activities for Students Who Finish Work Early

According to Tucker (2013) stated that technology shouldn't be something else you have to add to your already full plate. Instead, use technology to replace and improve what you already do. For example, a teacher who traditionally creates a handout with a series of comprehension questions could, instead, post a discussion question online using a discussion board or discussion platform. (Nina, 2019) Set up learning stations to energize and bolster students working at their very own pace. In the event that an students completes a task early, as opposed to being stuck trusting that different students will get up to speed or class to end, students can broaden and improve their learning by visiting a learning station and watching recordings, playing learning-based games, or investigating other online exercises identified with their learning.

Making Most of Games and Perks of Gamification

Gupta (2016) this is the best part about tech integration. The thing that students get to learn while gaming is the best thing. No doubts about the thing that how much love kids have for the games and here educational games are there to help students learn their important lessons while playing amazing games. Students can get motivated by challenging each other and if done on a mobile device, students are more likely to continue learning outside of the classroom. Using educational games is one of the best ways to use technology in the classroom to make students eager for learning. Learning can and should be fun and using technology for gamified learning in your classroom can be advantageous to achieving that goal. And while learning software can be a great teaching tool, gamified learning can also be as simple as creating a virtual scavenger hunt by coming up with a list of questions for students to search and find the correct answers for and adding students to pairs or groups to encourage collaboration and teamwork (Nina, 2019).

DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION

Just as everyone has a unique fingerprint, every student has an individual learning style. Chances are, not all of your students grasp a subject in the same way or share the same level of ability. Differentiating instruction means teaching the same material to all students using a variety of instructional strategies, or it may require the teacher to deliver lessons at varying levels of difficulty based on the ability of each student. (Weselby, 2014). To address individual student needs, teachers also provide appropriate scaffolding when working with content by teaching

prerequisite content to some students, allowing advanced students to move ahead of the class, or even changing the content for some students based on their individualized education programs (Tomlinson & Imbeau, 2010).

Teach with diverse materials

Avoid using one text for the entire class. Instead, use multiple texts at diverse reading levels for your units of study. This will enable every student to gather information from books and magazines they can truly read (Robb, 2003; Worthy et al., 1999).

Flexible grouping

According to miller (2018) flexible grouping is a teaching "best practice" that allows your students to team up according to their learning level. It gives you the opportunity to focus and zero-in on certain skills and objectives according to student need, making differentiated instruction possible. However, choosing how to level your students, or even which flexible grouping strategy will work best for your lesson, can be daunting. First, know grouping comes in two forms: Homogeneous and Heterogeneous. Depending on the activity, some educators prefer to mix the groups so that students of all levels are represented in each group (heterogeneous grouping of students), while others prefer organizing the students by ability levels (homogeneous grouping of students). Each approach has its strengths and drawbacks, and the decision whether to form instructional groups with students of similar or mixed ability depends on the purpose of the learning activity at hand. Cox (2019) Today, teachers are discovering that grouping and regrouping students in a variety of ways throughout the school day actually makes their job easier, and makes their students more productive. Flexible grouping is more than just moving a students' seat, it is practical way to differentiate as learning needs dictate. Flexible grouping is a range of grouping students together for delivering instruction. This can be as a whole class, a small group, or with a partner. Flexible grouping creates temporary groups that can last an hour, a week, or even a month. It's not permanent, but it is a temporary way for students to work together in a variety of ways and configurations depending upon activity and learning outcomes. In order to successfully differentiate instruction through flexible grouping, teachers must consider student learning profiles. In order to promote maximum learning, students need to move frequently among groups according to their specific needs.

Write to explore, think, learn, and improve comprehension

Learners can write only what they know and understand (Alvermann & Phelps, 1998; Robb, 2002; Self, 1987; Vaughan & Estes, 1986). If they haven't absorbed a lesson, they will have little to write. It's crucial for teachers to know that everyone in a class does not absorb the same information from a demonstration or a lesson (Clay, 1993). Reading students' journals can provide insights into whether students can think inferentially and analyze chunks of text. These insights support planning interventions for individuals, pairs, small groups, and, at times, the entire class (Robb, 2003).

Differentiated assessment

RIR (2015) viewed that differentiated assessment modify and match assessment with the varied characteristics or

profiles of students in order to meet the students' individual needs, thereby enhancing their learning and boosting their ability to show what they have learned. Students differ in their previous learning experiences, readiness, learning styles, preferences, academic standing, abilities, strengths and weaknesses, culture, race, and backgrounds. Teachers use differentiated assessment to match and respond to the varying learning needs of diverse students in a classroom. Designing various assessments apt for specific groups of learners provides more opportunities for students to effectively demonstrate what they have learned.

Student-Centered approach

McCarthy (2015) elaborated that student-centered classrooms include students in planning, implementation, and assessments. Involving the learners in these decisions will place more work on them, which can be a good thing. Teachers must become comfortable with changing their leadership style from directive to consultative. Bogler (2018) stated that allowing students to, with some adult guidance, choose what they want to learn and how they want to learn it gives them more control over their lives. This can eliminate resistance, help frustrated kids become more cooperative, and show all children that learning doesn't have to be boring.

Inquiry based learning

The key to success for students is making sure they are engaged with any material they are learning (enrichment, 2018). According to Gawron (2016) teaching must be more than asking a student what he or she wants to know. It's about triggering curiosity. And activating a student's curiosity. Inquiry based learning is mainly involving the learner and leading him to understand. Inquiry here implies on the possessing skills and attitude of yours, which allows you to ask questions about new resolutions and issues while you are gaining new information, inquiry-based teaching focuses on moving students beyond general curiosity into the realms of critical thinking and understanding. You must encourage students to ask questions and support them through the investigation process, understanding when to begin and how to structure an inquiry activity (Guido, 2017).

Conclusions

Sustaining evidence shows that 21st century educators need to adopt the new approaches in teaching and its strategy. Technology in the classroom, differentiated instruction and student centered approach should be adapted and modeled across the country to elevate and nourish the capability of the students to go beyond limitation. Pedagogies are constantly evolving and educators must also evolve from traditional teaching to 21st century teaching.

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